

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Using virtual experiments to improve data analysis

To cite this article: Finn Hughes *et al* 2025 *Meas. Sci. Technol.* **36** 046005

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [Virtual experiments for the assessment of data analysis and uncertainty quantification methods in scatterometry](#)
Gertjan Kok, Marcel van Dijk, Gerd Wübbeler *et al.*
- [NONLINEAR COLOR-METALLICITY RELATIONS OF GLOBULAR CLUSTERS. IV. TESTING THE NONLINEARITY SCENARIO FOR COLOR BIMODALITY VIA HST/WFC3 *u*-BAND PHOTOMETRY OF M84 \(NGC 4374\)](#)
Suk-Jin Yoon, Sangmo T. Sohn, Hak-Sub Kim *et al.*
- [Achieving robustness to aleatoric uncertainty with heteroscedastic Bayesian optimisation](#)
Ryan-Rhys Griffiths, Alexander A Aldrick, Miguel Garcia-Ortegon *et al.*

UNITED THROUGH SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY

 The Electrochemical Society
Advancing solid state & electrochemical science & technology

**248th
ECS Meeting**
Chicago, IL
October 12-16, 2025
Hilton Chicago

**Science +
Technology +
YOU!**

**SUBMIT
ABSTRACTS by
March 28, 2025**

SUBMIT NOW

Using virtual experiments to improve data analysis

Finn Hughes*

Mathematical Modelling and Data Analysis, Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt, Abbestraße 2-12, 10587 Berlin, Germany

E-mail: finn.hughes@ptb.de

Received 22 October 2024, revised 14 February 2025

Accepted for publication 11 March 2025

Published 20 March 2025

CrossMark

Abstract

In the data analysis of measurements, the simplified assumption of homoscedastic Gaussian noise is often made to account for the random fluctuations between observations. This may be an inadequate assumption which can deteriorate the results of a data analysis. Repeated measurements, which can be used to infer the true distribution of the data, may be inaccessible, making the true distribution hard to find. In such circumstances, thoroughly designed virtual experiments (VEs) can mimic real and possibly complex measurement processes to infer the true data distribution, which can subsequently be accounted for in an improved analysis of real observations. We explore the potential benefit of such an approach in terms of a metrological application, the tilted-wave interferometer (TWI). Our VE for the TWI yields not just the mean of the data, but also their physically modelled, random fluctuations arising in repeated observations. We use the virtual data to derive a statistical data model that includes correlations and heteroscedasticity. In applying a Bayesian data analysis procedure utilising said statistical model in conjunction with a vague prior for the quantity of interest, virtual data with a known ground truth are analysed and the quality of the resulting estimates are assessed. In addition, a comparison is carried out to the often-employed, simplified approach assuming homoscedastic, independent noise. We observe a significant improvement in the results when a more adequate statistical model for the data is utilised, along with a reliable uncertainty quantification. The work proposes the idea to extend the utilisation of a VE to inferring the noise characteristics of real observations, in turn leading to significantly improved data analysis procedures. The potential benefit is demonstrated to be substantial in terms of the considered metrological case study. Future research is discussed, including other ways that VEs could be used to further improve data analysis.

Keywords: virtual experiments, Bayesian uncertainty evaluation, statistical data analysis, Monte Carlo

* Author to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

Original Content from this work may be used under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 licence](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). Any further distribution of this work must maintain attribution to the author(s) and the title of the work, journal citation and DOI.

1. Introduction

A tool increasing in prominence in modern metrology is the virtual experiment (VE) [1–3]. A particular use arises, for example, in the circumstance where obtaining a sufficiently large sample size of real observations is economically or logistically unfeasible. Simulated observations can instead be generated through the VE to serve as an adequate replica of the real data. There are numerous applications for VEs in measurement sciences, including in sensitivity analyses to determine the size and significance of uncertainty sources [4], or uncertainty evaluations of the measurand or quantity of interest [5, 6]. VEs also possess a range of industrial applications such as the improvement of production processes [7], computational simulations of data at previously unobserved model settings [8], or safety and risk assessments where the cost of repetition and the potential endangerment of personnel impede obtaining a statistically necessary number of observations [9].

In metrology, VEs support the development of novel and improved measurement systems. For instance, in scenarios where knowledge that was previously required is unknown, such as the actual measurement model, VEs of a certain form can be utilised to provide a valid uncertainty evaluation following uncertainty frameworks in metrology [10–12] or the Bayesian paradigm [13, 14]. Furthermore, VEs through their ability to generate data are not restricted by the potentially limited availability of existing observations, and allow the user to control input parameters to assess the relevant behaviours of their measurement process, device, or instrument [15]. These examples show how VEs can be employed to support the understanding of complex measurement procedures and to improve their data analyses.

Data analysis is ubiquitous across all of science, particularly in metrology and the engineering sciences. Across various fields, fast, accurate, and cost-effective inferences in a variety of statistical tasks are required. An example of such a task is parameter estimation, where observations are used to determine model parameters for which the observations themselves are dependent on [16]. There are many techniques one can adopt in parameter estimation, such as least squares (LS) and maximum likelihood (ML) estimation [17]. Alternatively, one can apply a Bayesian procedure [18], which lends itself in a natural way to the quantification of the uncertainty associated with a derived estimate. In metrology, numerous other examples of parameter estimation procedures have been established for a variety of measurement applications, including concepts for sequential parameter estimation [16], model-based spectral estimation [19], and methods for ordinary differential equation models [20]. LS estimation (equivalent to ML estimation for Gaussian observations under the assumption of independence and homoscedasticity, i.e. uncorrelated and with identical variance [17]) is the method of estimation most frequently used due to its relative simplicity for linear problems. However, it has its deficiencies, for instance its highly sensitive nature with respect to outliers [21]. Furthermore, LS relies on the often inadequate assumption of homoscedasticity, which if violated yields larger errors and hence a lower quality of data analysis. This can be avoided

through using ML or a Bayesian inference, provided that an appropriate statistical model is available. It would therefore be of profound use if one were to establish a method whereby more information regarding the data could be utilised to improve the data analysis through attaining an adequate statistical model.

In the majority of VE applications, the VE itself is treated as a deterministic function. This is insufficient if one wishes to achieve a likelihood needed for analysis methods such as ML or a Bayesian inference. A solution could be to model the real observations through an assumed statistical model. However, if such a phenomenologically assigned statistical model does not sufficiently describe the distribution of the real data, the resulting data analysis procedure can be inadequate. A rigorous, physical model of an experiment as a basis of a VE, in combination with random elements entering the VE, is therefore required to guarantee the generated virtual data mimic the distribution of the real observations adequately. The inclusion of an additional probabilistic element following a homoscedastic Gaussian distribution to account for noise in data analysis has been applied recently in cases where VEs are used in conjunction with real measurements, e.g. [22, 23]. However, this can have potential issues in cases where the homoscedastic Gaussian assumption for the errors is not the most appropriate option. The benefits of accounting for correlation and/or heteroscedasticity in the aim of enhancing estimation are well known in statistics [24–26]. Indeed, adequate correlation and heteroscedasticity should be inherent in an adequate statistical model. VEs realistically modelling the random noise in real observations allow one to recognise and quantify these properties of the simulated observations, which in turn allows for more efficient analysis procedures to be developed. By extending VEs through physically modelled, random elements, leading to a distribution of virtual data closely resembling the distribution of real observations, an adequate statistical model can be deduced and utilised for an improved data analysis, leading to more accurate estimates and reduced uncertainties.

The aim of the paper is to show how VEs can help reduce estimation errors through the simple extension of current error models. Our proposed analysis method utilises knowledge regarding heteroscedasticity and correlations gained from an extended VE for the estimation of the quantity of interest in metrological applications. Through a common Bayesian estimator and heteroscedastic error model which accounts for correlations between data points, results portray a marked improvement in the accuracy of estimates and the reduction of uncertainties in our proposal compared to the same estimator using an error model with more simplified assumptions about the distributions of the data. The novelty provided by the research is that a physically relevant VE can be used to obtain partial or even full knowledge of the real covariance, which can be subsequently used to enhance the data analysis.

The paper is structured as follows: section 2 provides a definition of an extended VE and discusses the areas where current data analysis could be improved through using such a VE, section 3 presents the employed estimator for our practical application, and section 4 illustrates the application's results. Finally, some conclusions are drawn from the findings

in this paper, which motivate potential future directions of research.

2. VEs

A VE generates virtual data using assumed values for all inputs to mimic a real experiment. Often, some of these inputs constitute the quantities of interest (i.e. the measurand), which are to be inferred from the observed data, while other input quantities act as nuisance parameters instead. The virtual data can then be used to draw valid conclusions about the overall measurement procedure. Despite the increasing usage of VEs in metrology [10], it can be argued that there is not an agreed definition for what constitutes a VE. In this section, we clarify what our interpretation of a VE model is, as well as expressing some of the issues with frequently made data analysis assumptions that could be improved through appropriate usage of our interpretation of VEs.

2.1. Model

Adopting a similar model with different notation to the proposal featured in [11], a general statistical model for the virtual data produced by a VE can formally be written as:

$$x^{\text{ve}} \sim G(\theta, z, w). \quad (1)$$

Virtual data x^{ve} are generated by the VE itself through the deterministic function G for given values of all (physical) inputs of the VE. Included in the input quantities of G are θ , the actual measurand i.e. the quantity of interest, and z , additional input parameters (also known as nuisance parameters) that influence the measurement. Both θ and z should be viewed as fixed but unknown. Random fluctuations are accounted for by the random entities w , which can be stated as $w \sim F(W)$. The w parameters represent physical inputs within the VE that cannot be kept fixed in repeated observations and hence impact the variability of simulated observations. Observational noise and other quantifiable fluctuations would also be represented within the distribution of w . The notation $w \sim F(W)$ simply states that these random fluctuations follow a certain distribution that needs to be assigned based on the physical understanding of the behaviour of those inputs. While the distribution of w is often assumed to be Gaussian, the choice of distribution is not limited to this case, and hence could be represented by a variety of multivariate parameters. It should also be noted that w may be a vector exceeding the dimensions of the output when part of a nonlinear model.

Random virtual data are produced by randomly drawing a value for w , and subsequently evaluating the function G . By accounting for the truly varying physical quantities in the experiment via this procedure, it enables us to arrive at a realistic distribution of the virtual data, albeit requiring a thorough understanding of the underlying physical processes and their implementation in the VE.

The forward model, that is the mean of the virtual data for fixed parameters θ and z of the VE when w is a zero-mean linear term within the statistical model (1), has no explicit

dependency on the w parameters. Due to this lack of dependency, the forward model will under repetition generate the same output values when the input values for θ and z remain constant. However, despite the lack of influence on the forward model, the w parameters are still an internal part of the VE, as can be seen in the schematic diagram in figure 1, and should not be considered to be an additional separate term to account for systematic errors. This means that even with keeping values for θ and z fixed, the VE as a whole will under repetition generate fluctuating output values. The roles of each of the inputs in the statistical model (1) can perhaps be most easily illustrated through an example of a simple physical experiment from optics, in which θ represents a parameterisation of an optical surface for which the precise form is to be determined. The data x^{ve} could be camera intensities upon an optical interferometric measurement procedure. The z parameters are nuisance parameters that influence the procedure but are not directly of interest, such as an angle of the camera lens. Finally, w could be the wavelength of the laser—a parameter that fluctuates in repeated measurements.

2.2. Modelling assumptions

There are a number of typical assumptions made during data analyses involving VEs to help simplify complex processes. There is often logical reasoning behind these assumptions and simplifications, such as to summarise non-significant parameters so as to save time and cost during simulations [27]. A prime example of an aforementioned assumption is additive homoscedastic Gaussian noise added during the analysis phase. This term accounts for the random fluctuations that occur with each measurement for unquantifiable reasons. Such random noise is necessary for an adequate analysis of real data. An example of said Gaussian noise when VEs operate in conjunction with real measurements in an analysis is given in [10].

Although the assumption of homoscedasticity helps maintain a simplicity to the analysis, and would undoubtedly be convenient if it consistently provided suitable results, it is unfortunately not always appropriate. Many multivariate statistical models have inconsistent variances between data points, meaning modelling the data as having a single constant variance would be inadequate.

Another assumption that is often made during data analyses is that the noise is assumed to possess independence between all data points. However, this assumption can be violated, with data points frequently producing some correlations. While traditionally noise processes are assumed to be independent from the perspective of measurement noise, some metrological problems define such noises as perturbations. Therefore, in such scenarios, it would seem unsuitable to assume complete independence between the data. By failing to accommodate information regarding these possibly influential correlations, the assumption of independence may result in poorer estimates. This issue, along with the inadequacy of the assumption of homoscedasticity, will be illustrated in our metrological application presented in section 4.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram on the definition of a VE.

3. Data analysis

3.1. Method

In this section, we establish our data analysis method that we applied to our practical example. The approach can be broken down into three steps:

- (1) Derive the Bayes estimator for the measurand/quantity of interest.
- (2) Use the repeated simulations of the VE data obtained through Monte Carlo sampling to conduct the analysis through the estimator derived in (1).
- (3) Assess the results through the accuracy and adequacy of the derived uncertainties.

First, we establish our estimator. In section 2.1, we defined a general VE model. Using the same notation, we can define our statistical model for generating simulated observations, $x^{ve}|\mu$. Here, measurand θ and nuisance parameters z are combined in the vector $\mu = (\theta, z)$. We define X as being the $n \times p$ ‘design matrix’ in the assumed linear relationship between the p parameters, μ , and the mean of the data, $X\mu$. This linear relationship is part of our statistical model and constitutes an approximation, which in our case turns out to be sufficient for our nonlinear, metrological application. In other cases, a nonlinear forward model needs to be included in the statistical model, which complicates the estimation process and the numerical calculations but still falls within our approach, see for instance appendix D. The w parameters, which are, additionally to the random fluctuations, physically relevant inputs to the VE, are here assumed to feature in our statistical model in the form of an additive Gaussian error term with covariance Γ . The VE allows one to infer the true value of Γ through the variability and correlations of repeated simulations. The statistical model for the (real or virtual) data, which in our example follows a Gaussian distribution, can hence be expressed mathematically as such:

$$x^{ve}|\mu \sim N(X\mu, \Gamma). \quad (2)$$

The statistical model (2) can thus be stated as follows:

$$x^{ve} = X\mu + w,$$

where $w \sim N(0, \Gamma)$, which may be a vector summarising multiple physically relevant inputs and noise contributions.

We will refer to the model where the covariance in the statistical analysis is considered homoscedastic as the *simplified statistical model*. Here, one would assume that $\Gamma = \sigma^2 I_n$, where σ^2 represents the variance of all virtual data points. By contrast, the *proposed statistical model* refers to the procedure where heteroscedasticity and correlations are quantified in the covariance matrix of the statistical model. The covariance matrix Γ is determined to be the covariance of the virtual data produced by the complex VE¹.

It should be noted that the statistical model (2) is an approximation of the true distribution of our complex virtual model, i.e. the distribution of the virtual data may not follow exactly a Gaussian distribution, and the linear forward model of the statistical model is an approximation as well. The numerical results in section 4, however, suggest that the model can be seen as a sufficiently accurate approximation of the true distribution of the virtual data.

A Bayesian inference is applied for both statistical models, the simplified and the proposed, with the only difference being the choice of covariance matrix. Such a Bayesian inference for a statistical, linear model of the form given in the statistical model (2) is well established in literature [28]. In our example, we assume the measurand and nuisance parameters follow independent Gaussian prior distributions $\theta \sim N(\mu_\theta, \Sigma_\theta)$ and $z \sim N(\mu_z, \Sigma_z)$ respectively. Hence, the joint prior distribution and covariance of μ for our example is as given:

$$\mu \sim N(\mu_0, V), \mu_0 = \begin{pmatrix} \mu_\theta \\ \mu_z \end{pmatrix}, V = \begin{pmatrix} \Sigma_\theta & 0 \\ 0 & \Sigma_z \end{pmatrix}.$$

A vague prior is chosen for θ to model the prior less informatively. It was revealed through conducting a sensitivity analysis that the data was the dominant influence on the results in section 4 rather than the choice of prior. With the z parameters, given our pre-existing knowledge of our practical example, a more specific choice of prior is made to reflect the prior knowledge about these input quantities.

¹ The virtual data were produced for values of μ equal to the mean of the prior for μ .

A Bayesian analysis was chosen because it allows for prior knowledge to be included, which is often available, e.g. about the z parameters. Advantages of a Bayesian inference are that it results in a full distribution for the measurand, that it naturally lends itself to an uncertainty evaluation, and that it allows probability statements to be made about the measurand conditional on the observed data.

Note that when applying JCGM documentation regarding guidance for uncertainty evaluation in metrology, the z parameters act as additional input quantities, for which estimates and variances [29] or a whole distribution [30, 31] need to be assigned. In our Bayesian analysis, such prior knowledge about the z parameters can be naturally included. Regarding the measurand, i.e. the θ parameters, a vague prior is chosen such that the results are insensitive to the actual choice of prior and are dominated by the data. This also reflects the approach of the JCGM documentation, cf [32–34]. Finally, it is also to note that the Bayes estimate of μ for the homoscedastic model reduces to the LS estimate when a vague prior is also chosen for z such that the data completely dominate the estimate.

3.2. Estimator

Given for our practical example that the prior and likelihood follow Gaussian distributions, one can state explicitly the estimator for the parameter values of interest in our Bayesian data analysis. Using the quantities as defined previously, the formula for the estimator can be given:

$$\hat{\mu} = V_{\mu} (X^T \Gamma^{-1} x^{ve} + V^{-1} \mu_0), \quad (3)$$

with V_{μ} being the covariance of our estimator written as such:

$$V_{\mu} = (X^T \Gamma^{-1} X + V^{-1})^{-1}. \quad (4)$$

The derivation of the estimator can be found in appendix A.

Through probability calculus, the marginal distribution for θ can be achieved by integrating out the nuisance parameters. In the case of a Gaussian posterior, this leads to a Gaussian distribution as well, where the mean and covariance matrix are obtained by simply taking the corresponding components of $\hat{\mu}$ and the corresponding block matrix of V_{μ} . Estimates and uncertainties for the quantity of interest are easily determined in this way, cf appendix A. The Bayesian analyses for the two statistical models both adopt this estimator, with the only difference between the approaches being the choice of Γ .

4. Results

4.1. Tilted-wave interferometer (TWI)

To compare the contrasting statistical models in a practical sense, we used data simulated using a complex metrological application where VEs are utilised, namely the TWI. This optical metrology instrument can reconstruct a surface-under-test through solving high-dimensional nonlinear inverse problems by comparing real surface observations and predicted

data [35, 36]. The measurement concepts of the TWI can be replicated in a virtual environment, where the generated data, the optical path differences (OPDs), closely resemble the observed OPDs from the real TWI [14]. A sketch of the TWI showing the optical paths followed as well as the instrument's parameters is given in figure 2. For this research, the OPDs of 5517 pixels belonging to a toroid were simulated for 5000 runs of the virtual TWI. From this, we selected 15 random pixels, highlighted in figure 3, which would form an observable sample set that covers a large scope of the specimen-under-test (SUT). The z parameters considered include the orientation of the SUT, with the covariance values for each parameter determined using the standard uncertainties outlined in [14]. The w parameters considered represent parameters such as wavelength which cannot be fixed under repeated measurement. The random fluctuations are sampled from the distribution of the virtual differential OPDs (DOPDs), and subsequently used to infer the covariance matrix Γ . The matrix Γ is then used in our Gaussian statistical model that approximates the true distribution of the data. The design matrix X is calculated through the linearisation of the nonlinear, complex VE model. The assumption of linearity in the statistical model has been found previously to be adequate when using the virtual TWI within certain ranges of its parameters [4]. It is to note that the linearisation made is possible when the TWI is reduced as in our example, and it is not just a convenient approximation. θ is a vector representing a parameterisation of the SUT, e.g. coefficients of the Zernike polynomials. In our example, θ is considered to have 5 components. It should be clarified that the complex VE of the TWI is used for simulations in this paper, with a proxy of the 'exact' statistical model used in the data analysis. The analysis model therefore includes a linear approximation of the true forward model, yet is realistic for the application to real observations.

Displayed in figure 4 are the distributions of the virtual DOPDs at 3 of the 15 pixel positions in the subset of the complex VE of the TWI, as well as approximate distributions using either homoscedastic variance across all pixels (red) or a variance adjusted for each individual pixel (blue). Here, one can observe the insufficiency of the homoscedastic Gaussian assumption. The maintained variance fails to adequately imitate any of the selected pixels' variances, while accounting for the variance on a pixel-by-pixel basis yields a more accurate reflection of the actual distributions. Figure 5 illustrates the magnitude of the correlation in repeated virtual observations between the 15 considered pixels, with the strength in correlation between two pixels indicated by the shade of the corresponding square. This correlation plot suggests another potential issue with the assumption of independence. Even though there is no clear relation between the size of correlation and the proximity of the pixels, assuming complete independence between pixels would be inadequate given there is clearly strong correlation between certain pixels (e.g. Pixel 4 and Pixel 15, or Pixel 12 and Pixel 3). The relation between pixels should therefore be on some level accounted for in the assumed statistical model employed for the estimation process. Using data from our practical example (the complex VE of the TWI), we are able to derive the correlation pattern of the data points (the

Figure 2. Plot of the TWI setup including the optical paths, as given in [14]. Reproduced from [14]. CC BY 4.0.

Figure 3. Plot of the coordinate positions of the 5517 pixels measured using the virtual TWI. The 15 pixels selected to form the subset are highlighted in black.

pixels), as well as the variance pertaining to each individual pixel. This will enable significant improvement to be made to the quality of the data analysis when utilised through the proposed statistical model.

The potential benefit arising from our proposed statistical model can be demonstrated through the accuracy of the derived estimates and the size of the corresponding uncertainties. Furthermore, we can compare the dependence each statistical model's analysis has on the correlations and heteroscedasticity to explore the enhancement our proposed statistical model provides.

4.2. Monte Carlo sampling

Monte Carlo sampling on the basis of the VE was carried out for the generation of test problems. The advantage of analysing such data is that the value of the measurand is known and hence the accuracy of estimates, as well as the adequacy of calculated uncertainties, can be quantitatively assessed. It should be noted that the complex VE of the TWI has been shown to produce virtual data that mimic real data in a realistic fashion [27], reinforcing that our conclusions, albeit not drawn from real data, are nevertheless meaningful.

Each single test problem was simulated as follows. Values for parameters θ and z were assigned, before data were calculated as the sum of $X\mu$. Additionally, for the realisation of w , an actual repetition of the complex VE has been used to circumvent an *inverse crime* by not using the same model for data generation and inference. To ensure all results were not based on a single choice of values for θ and z , different values for these parameters were used in each simulation, each drawn from their respective prior distributions. In this case, 95% of the credible intervals for θ will cover the true value of θ , cf appendix B, and we can thus assess quantitatively how well our proxy statistical model matches the true distribution of the data in terms of the reliability of calculated uncertainties.

For each assessment, 10 000 test problems were simulated, each with different values for the parameters and with a different realisation of the noise, before being subsequently analysed.

4.3. Accuracy

The absolute estimation error serves as an indication of the overall accuracy of the respective estimators. For each test problem, the mean of the absolute error across the 5 components of θ was calculated.

The box plots in figure 6 indicate a significant reduction in estimation error when using the heteroscedastic proposed statistical model. The mean of the absolute estimation errors for the Bayesian analysis method involving the simplified statistical model was calculated to be over 6 times greater than the mean of the proposed statistical model's estimation errors. Furthermore, the interquartile range of the absolute estimation errors was notably larger for the simplified statistical model's analysis than for the proposal (1.66×10^{-6} to 3.75×10^{-7} respectively to 3 significant figures). These diagnostics are strong evidence that the proposed statistical model results in more accurate estimations than the simplified approach.

4.4. Uncertainty

Another statistical assessment that would be useful when quantifying any improvements in estimation could regard the actual coverage probability of the uncertainty intervals, which quantify the range of uncertainty belonging to each of the

Figure 4. Density plots for the variance of 3 pixels of the virtual TWI. The grey bars indicate the density of DOPDs that fit within the bars’ intervals on the x-axis. The homoscedastic Gaussian fit has been indicated in red, while the Gaussian model where the variance depends solely on the individual pixel is indicated in blue.

Figure 5. A plot of the absolute correlation between the 15 pixels which form a subset of the virtual TWI.

respective parameters’ estimates. When averaging over the prior distribution, it can be proven that the coverage probability of credible intervals is equal to the chosen credibility (see appendix B). Even accounting for the analysis model used for our data analysis being an approximation, one would expect reasonable coverage probabilities for the uncertainty intervals to come to fruition. Further details on the method of calculating the estimated coverage probabilities are provided in appendix C.

In figure 7, one can see the coverage probabilities of the 95% uncertainty intervals generated for the 5 parameters of θ , our measurand. Both models’ methods deviated consistently

from the indicated 95% benchmark, however the proposed statistical model only differed by a few percentage points for each parameter, with probabilities in the range [94.1%, 99.5%] (3 significant figures). By contrast, there was a larger variability amongst the coverage probabilities of the Bayesian analysis involving the homoscedastic-assuming simplified statistical model, with probabilities in the range [65.9%, 98.9%]. This can be interpreted that the uncertainty intervals of the proposed model tend to approximate closer to 95% (the desired coverage probability) than the intervals of the simplified model, and with less risk of significant deviation (such as in parameter 4 of the simplified model’s intervals in figure 7). Although there is greater consistency across the coverage probabilities of the analysis involving the proposed statistical model, it is arguable that the performance of the simplified model is not drastically worse when context regarding the approximation made for both statistical models is taken into account. As shown in parameter 3 in figure 7, there are even occasions where exceptional coverage is provided by the intervals of the simplified model. However, figure 8 displays the size of each of the uncertainty intervals for the respective procedures, which provides further insight which clearly supports the use of the proposed statistical model. Across each parameter, the interval sizes are greater when a homoscedastic and uncorrelated covariance is assumed. This is particularly relevant for parameter 1, where the true coverage probability was actually closer to the desired 95% for the simplified statistical model (96.9% compared to 99.5%, 3 significant figures). This gain in coverage accuracy is offset by the large uncertainty, which is over 9 times greater in the simplified statistical model’s analysis method than its counterpart from the analysis of the proposed statistical model. This also offers a clear explanation for the near-full coverage provided by the simplified statistical model for parameter

Figure 6. Box plots of the estimation errors for the two estimators.

Figure 7. Plot of the proportion of the estimates covered by each of the calculated uncertainty intervals for each measurand parameter. The red line represents the Bayesian analysis involving the simplified statistical model, while the blue line represents the Bayesian analysis involving the proposed statistical model.

3, where the uncertainty interval is the largest amongst all obtained intervals (7.99×10^{-6} to 3 significant figures). The difference in lengths of the measurement uncertainty intervals corresponds almost identically to the difference in accuracy shown in figure 6 (given that the coverage probabilities established in figure 7 are reasonable). Thus, adopting the proposed statistical model and incorporating heteroscedasticity and correlations into the estimation procedure yields more accurate estimates with reduced uncertainty.

4.5. Influence of correlations

While there is a reduction in error shown in figure 6 for the proposed statistical model, it is useful to reinforce that the improvement is attributable to the covariances between pixels.

This can be portrayed through, for example, a clear relationship between the change in correlation size and the accuracy.

Figure 9 provides such a depiction, highlighting the influence of assuming independence specifically in our replica TWI application. The covariances in the employed statistical model between the 15 pixels in the ‘real’ covariance Γ are scaled by factor $\lambda \in [0, 1]$, with the diagonal of the matrix (the heteroscedastic variances of each individual pixel) remaining constant and unchanged. For example, at $\lambda = 0$, the assumed covariance for the analysis would be assuming full independence, while at $\lambda = 1$ the full real covariance matrix is considered. The results exhibit that as the percentage of pixel-by-pixel covariances accounted for increases, the error of the estimation process is reduced. One can see assuming independence between data points greatly inhibits the potential

Figure 8. Plot of the size of the calculated uncertainty intervals for each measurand parameter. The red line represents the Bayesian analysis involving the simplified statistical model, while the blue line represents the Bayesian analysis involving the proposed statistical model.

Figure 9. Plot of the estimation error as the correlations in the employed statistical model between the pixels are scaled by factor $\lambda \in [0, 1]$. At $\lambda = 0$, the assumed covariance for the analysis would be assuming full independence, while at $\lambda = 1$ the full real covariance matrix is considered. The dashed black line indicates the mean absolute error of the estimates produced using the homoscedastic covariance.

accuracy of the estimation procedure. In our TWI application, while there is a minor improvement registered by even just assuming heteroscedastic variances for each pixel rather than a single homoscedastic variance, the major improvement is provided by disregarding the commonly-adopted independence assumption. Heteroscedasticity appears to have a relatively minor effect on improving the estimation procedure, particularly compared to the sizeable benefit yielded through accounting for existing correlations. However, it is important to stress that, while the discrepancy between the influence of correlations and the influence of overall heteroscedasticity is stark in the case-specific TWI example, the scale of effect corresponding to heteroscedasticity could be more significant in a

different application. In any case, there is a sizeable advantage to be gained if one incorporates an adequate statistical model in the estimation process.

5. Discussion

Across the considered metrics, the proposed statistical model accounting for correlations and heteroscedasticity yields superior estimations compared to the simplified statistical model. This is shown distinctly in the accuracy of the respective estimators. Furthermore, the uncertainty is almost ten-fold greater for certain parameters when

using the simplified model, further supporting usage of the proposal.

In order to achieve these benefits, a carefully modelled VE is required, which can be a challenge. Clear distinction between the VE's fixed parameters and the parameters that fluctuate need to be made. The fluctuating parameters also require an assigned distribution, which necessitates substantial metrological knowledge about the experiment in question. A solution to such a problem could revolve around altering the variance of the random fluctuations (w parameters) in the employed VE and adjusting in comparison with real repeated measurements.

For our practical application, we have assumed a linear model and Gaussian priors for all parameters, which subsequently yields the analytically available estimator given in equation (3). However, although these assumptions should not be considered convenient approximations for the TWI, many other metrological applications would require a nonlinear forward model or non-Gaussian priors. Provided that the step procedure outlined in section 3 is followed, estimation via Bayesian inference can still be conducted for these cases. However, the estimator, if existence can be ensured, may still not be analytically available. In such a circumstance, numerical tools such as Markov chain Monte Carlo sampling would need to be adopted. See also appendix D.

It is important to acknowledge again that it is well established in statistical literature that accommodating for the actual covariance in estimation, e.g. in Bayesian analysis or through ML estimation/weighted LS, is generally superior to homoscedastic estimation procedures [37]. However, to do so requires sufficient knowledge of the correlations or relationships between the data points, which has previously been unavailable in the circumstance where (many) repeated measurements are not possible. Through our interpretation of a physically sound VE, information regarding these statistical correlations can be delivered. Hence the importance of this research is that it highlights not only the evident benefits available when deviating from the assumption of homoscedastic Gaussian noise, but also how one can do so through the implementation of a VE.

There is some logic behind how the simplified assumptions have been adopted thus far in typical metrological applications involving a VE. Prioritising computational costs or simplicity of models would perhaps lead to one favouring a reduced version of the covariance, provided the primary purpose of the analysis featuring a VE is not accuracy but to instead draw valid general conclusions about the application in question. However, as we have demonstrated, there is considerable benefit to increasing the complexity of the modelling of real data—that is to say, factoring in heteroscedasticity and correlation. The improvement is arguably so large that it would be inappropriate to exclude the benefits and maintain the homoscedastic and independence assumptions in data analyses where a VE accounting for physically modelled fluctuations is present or usable, regardless of the primary goal. Although the simplified approach is far easier to employ, one would likely want to prioritise accuracy over simplicity

in practical measurement scenarios when the benefit is substantial.

6. Conclusion and outlook

We have shown that through using a thoroughly designed VE that accounts for physically modelled fluctuations, one can reduce the error in estimating the quantities of interest when the assumption of homoscedasticity or independence in a data analysis is inadequate. The accuracy and variability of an estimation process can be significantly improved by incorporating an adequate statistical model for the observed data, which is determined by a refined VE. Although we have demonstrated these deductions for only one optical metrology example, the example presented is a proof-of-principle study and the methodology is transferable to other VEs and data analysis models. By adopting the results of this paper into the application of VEs in data analysis, greater accuracies and lower uncertainties can be reached. In conclusion, the concepts introduced in this paper should be further explored and adopted into common practice.

Many directions of future research can extend from the removal of restrictive assumptions surrounding data analysis involving VE models. For example, it would be worthwhile to observe the influence of deviating from the Gaussian distribution entirely. Examining applications which diverge from the Gaussian distribution would not only confirm the current conclusions are applicable even when the estimator is unavailable analytically, but it would also allow one to determine other ways VEs could be used to yield a more realistic reflection of the data and hence sufficiently improve the data analysis, particularly in the presence of non-Gaussian data. From a practical perspective, future research regarding different metrological applications would be required.

Data availability statement

Data and software will be provided upon publication. The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by European Partnership on Metrology, co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme and by the Participating States, grant number 22DIT01 ViDiT. The authors would like to thank Ines Fortmeier for discussions about the TWI.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Appendix A. Proof of the derivation of the estimator

Given a VE of the form $x^{ve}|\mu \sim N(X\mu, \Gamma)$, the probability density function (PDF) of x^{ve} is:

$$f(x^{ve}|\mu) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{n/2} (\det \Gamma)^{1/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} (x^{ve} - X\mu)^T \Gamma^{-1} (x^{ve} - X\mu)\right).$$

Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} f(\mu|x^{ve}) &= f(x^{ve}|\mu) \times g(\mu) \\ &\propto \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} (x^{ve} - X\mu)^T \Gamma^{-1} (x^{ve} - X\mu)\right) \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} (\mu - \mu_0)^T V^{-1} (\mu - \mu_0)\right) \\ &= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left((x^{ve} - X\mu)^T \Gamma^{-1} (x^{ve} - X\mu) + (\mu - \mu_0)^T V^{-1} (\mu - \mu_0) \right)\right) \\ &= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left[(x^{ve})^T \Gamma^{-1} x^{ve} - (x^{ve})^T \Gamma^{-1} X\mu - \mu^T X^T \Gamma^{-1} x^{ve} + \mu^T X^T \Gamma^{-1} X\mu \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + \mu^T V^{-1} \mu - \mu_0^T V^{-1} \mu_0 - \mu_0^T V^{-1} \mu + \mu_0^T V^{-1} \mu_0 \right]\right) \\ &= \lambda_1 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left[-\left((x^{ve})^T \Gamma^{-1} X + \mu_0^T V^{-1} \right) \mu - \mu^T (X^T \Gamma^{-1} x^{ve} + V^{-1} \mu_0) + \mu^T (X^T \Gamma^{-1} X + V^{-1}) \mu \right]\right) \\ &= \lambda_2 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left[(\mu^T - ((x^{ve})^T \Gamma^{-1} X + \mu_0^T V^{-1}) V_\mu) V_\mu^{-1} (\mu - V_\mu (X^T \Gamma^{-1} x^{ve} + V^{-1} \mu_0)) \right]\right) \\ &= \lambda_2 \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \left[(\mu - \hat{\mu})^T V_\mu^{-1} (\mu - \hat{\mu}) \right]\right), \end{aligned}$$

where $V_\mu = (X^T \Gamma^{-1} X + V^{-1})$, $\hat{\mu} = V_\mu (X^T \Gamma^{-1} x^{ve} + V^{-1} \mu_0)$, and λ_1 and λ_2 are constant in terms of μ .

We hence find the MAP estimator, i.e. the value of μ for which $f(\mu|x^{ve})$ is maximum, to be $\hat{\mu}$.

The proposed analysis method will use the full covariance matrix Γ , while the simplified analysis method will just assume $\Gamma = \sigma^2 I_n$. One can marginalise with respect to θ by taking the corresponding components of $\hat{\mu}$ and the corresponding block matrix of V_μ .

Appendix B. Proof of perfect coverage when averaging over the prior

It can be proven that, when averaging over the prior, the posterior distribution yields perfect coverage. Let the data be denoted by y , the measurand be denoted by θ , and the credible region be denoted by CR . For the ease of notation, assume θ is univariate.

The coverage probability of a credible region CR for θ with credibility P , obtained by the marginal posterior for θ , can be stated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} P &= \int_{\theta \in CR} p(\theta|y) d\theta \\ &= \int_{\theta \in \mathfrak{R}} \mathbb{1}(\theta \in CR) p(\theta|y) d\theta. \end{aligned}$$

Given the prior $\mu \sim N(\mu_0, V)$, we also have the PDF of μ available:

$$g(\mu) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{n/2} (\det V)^{1/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} (\mu - \mu_0)^T V^{-1} (\mu - \mu_0)\right).$$

We can define the coverage probability taken over the data at θ_0 :

$$P_{\theta_0} = \int_{y \in \mathfrak{R}} p(y|\theta_0) \mathbb{1}(\theta_0 \in CR) dy.$$

Therefore, the expected value of P_{θ_0} , averaged over the prior, is:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\theta_0} [P_{\theta_0}] &= \int_{\theta_0 \in \mathfrak{R}} \pi(\theta_0) \left(\int_{y \in \mathfrak{R}} p(y|\theta_0) \mathbb{1}(\theta_0 \in CR) dy \right) d\theta_0 \\ &= \int_{y \in \mathfrak{R}} \int_{\theta_0 \in \mathfrak{R}} \pi(\theta_0) p(y|\theta_0) \mathbb{1}(\theta_0 \in CR) d\theta_0 dy \\ &= \int_{y \in \mathfrak{R}} \int_{\theta_0 \in \mathfrak{R}} \pi(\theta_0|y) \pi(y) \mathbb{1}(\theta_0 \in CR) d\theta_0 dy \\ &= \int_{y \in \mathfrak{R}} \left(\int_{\theta_0 \in \mathfrak{R}} \pi(\theta_0|y) \mathbb{1}(\theta_0 \in CR) d\theta_0 \right) \pi(y) dy \\ &= \int_{y \in \mathfrak{R}} \pi(y) P dy \\ &= P \int_{y \in \mathfrak{R}} \pi(y) dy \\ &= P. \end{aligned}$$

Appendix C. Coverage probability of an uncertainty interval

To assess the coverage probability in our example, we simply generate m estimates of θ as before, denoted $\hat{\theta} = (\hat{\theta}_1, \dots, \hat{\theta}_m)$. The 95% uncertainty interval size is equivalent to the product of the z -value $\Phi^{-1}(0.95)$, which is approximately 1.96, and the uncertainty of the estimator, which is its standard deviation. Therefore, the estimate of the coverage probability of the credible interval for parameter j can be expressed as:

$$\frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m \mathbb{1} \left(|\theta_j - (\hat{\theta}_i)_j| \leq 1.96 (V_\mu)_{jj}^{\frac{1}{2}} \right).$$

Appendix D. Generalisation of the data analysis method

In the statistical model (2) that has been used for the data analysis, i.e. the analysis model, the assumed linear relationship has been chosen to obtain analytical formulas for the estimator and demonstrate, in a proof-of-principle study, the impact of including the heteroscedasticity and correlations in the data by means of a VE. While the general VE in statistical model (1) is usually more complex, a simple analysis model may suffice to explain the parametric relationship in the available data. However, in more complex, nonlinear scenarios and with the availability of a more general forward model or forward response mapping $g(\mu)$ that maps the unknown parameter $\mu = (\theta, z)$ to the observed data in \mathbb{R}^n , the same methodology as in section 3 can be applied. Such a forward response mapping $g(\mu)$ may be derived from the complex VE in a numerical/approximate/surrogate modelling manner or by simply setting the random fluctuations in w to an estimated value $g(\mu) = g(\theta, z) = G(\theta, z, \hat{w})$.

Given such a forward response mapping, the analysis model may again be assumed to contain an additive noise component:

$$x^{\text{ve}} = g(\mu) + w, \quad w \sim \pi(w; \eta), \quad (5)$$

where the parameter η of the distribution of the noise component w can again be estimated using repeated evaluations of the VE $G(\theta, z, w)$ through Monte Carlo sampling for the physically relevant interpretation of w . One common example for the distribution of w is the Gaussian noise assumption $\pi(w; \eta) = N(w|0, \Gamma)$, with $\eta = \sigma^2$ for the homoscedastic case with covariance $\Gamma = \sigma^2 I$ and $\eta = (\Gamma_{i,j})_{i,j=1,\dots,n}$ for the heteroscedastic case with full covariance matrix Γ .

Following this setting, with an additionally assumed prior distribution $\pi(\mu)$ for the unknown parameter, a usual inference can be performed that applies Bayes theorem:

$$\pi(\mu|x^{\text{ve}}) \propto L(\mu|x^{\text{ve}}) \pi(\mu), \quad (6)$$

where the likelihood function L follows from the assumed statistical model (5). For ensuring existence of the posterior distribution $\pi(\mu|x^{\text{ve}})$, integrability of the likelihood function with respect to the prior is required, which can be ensured using properties of the noise distribution and the forward

response mapping [38]. See also [39] for a recent discussion on well-posedness of these Bayesian inverse problems. For the Gaussian noise case, the posterior PDF for the parameter μ reads as follows:

$$\pi(\mu|x^{\text{ve}}) \propto \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} (x^{\text{ve}} - g(\mu))^T \Gamma^{-1} (x^{\text{ve}} - g(\mu)) \right) \pi(w). \quad (7)$$

Due to the usual complex structure of the forward response mapping, sometimes only being available numerically, no analytical formula may be available for quantities of interest, such as the mean or standard deviation of θ contained in μ . Furthermore, samples of $\pi(\mu|x^{\text{ve}})$ may only be available through more sophisticated sampling strategies, such as Markov chain Monte Carlo [40].

ORCID iDs

Finn Hughes <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-5470-3705>
 Manuel Marschall <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0648-1936>
 Clemens Elster <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0113-3713>

References

- [1] Wright L and Davidson S 2024 Digital twins for metrology; metrology for digital twins *Meas. Sci. Technol.* **35** 051001
- [2] Sun H, Yang M and Wang H 2022 A virtual experiment for measuring system resilience: a case of chemical process systems *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.* **228** 108829
- [3] Liu G, Xu Q, Gao F, Guan Q and Fang Q 2008 Analysis of key technologies for virtual instruments metrology *Fourth Int. Symp. on Precision Mechanical Measurements* vol 7130 (SPIE) pp 1216–21
- [4] Fortmeier I, Stavridis M, Wiegmann A, Schulz M, Baer G, Pruss C, Osten W and Elster C 2013 Sensitivity analysis of tilted-wave interferometer asphere measurements using virtual experiments *Proc. SPIE* **8789** 878907
- [5] Heißelmann D, Franke M, Rost K, Wendt K, Kistner T and Schwehn C 2019 Determination of measurement uncertainty by Monte Carlo simulation *Advanced Mathematical and Computational Tools in Metrology and Testing X* (World Scientific) pp 192–202
- [6] van Dijk M and Kok G 2025 Comparison of uncertainty evaluation methods for virtual experiments with an application to a virtual CMM *Meas. Sens.* **101785**
- [7] Darius P L, Portier K M and Schrevers E 2007 Virtual experiments and their use in teaching experimental design *Int. Stat. Rev.* **75** 281–94
- [8] Bayarri M J, Berger J O, Calder E S, Dalbey K, Lunagomez S, Patra A K, Pitman E B, Spiller E T and Wolpert R L 2009 Using statistical and computer models to quantify volcanic hazards *Technometrics* **51** 402–13
- [9] Levy S and Steinberg D M 2010 Computer experiments: a review *AStA Adv. Stat. Anal.* **94** 311–24
- [10] Wübbeler G, Marschall M, Kniel K, Heißelmann D, Härtig F and Elster C 2022 GUM-compliant uncertainty evaluation using virtual experiments *Metrology* **2** 114–27
- [11] Hughes F, Marschall M, Wübbeler G, Kok G, van Dijk M and Elster C 2025 JCGM 101-compliant uncertainty evaluation using virtual experiments *Meas. Sens.* **101731**
- [12] Marschall M, Hughes F, Wübbeler G, Kok G, van Dijk M and Elster C 2024 Using a multivariate virtual experiment for uncertainty evaluation with unknown variance *Metrology* **4** 534–46

- [13] Heidenreich S, Gross H and Bär M 2015 Bayesian approach to the statistical inverse problem of scatterometry: comparison of three surrogate models *Int. J. Uncertain. Quantification* **5** 511–26
- [14] Marschall M, Fortmeier I, Stavridis M, Hughes F and Elster C 2024 Bayesian uncertainty evaluation applied to the tilted-wave interferometer *Opt. Express* **32** 18664–83
- [15] Harsch A, Pruss C, Baer G and Osten W 2019 Monte Carlo simulations: a tool to assess complex measurement systems *6th European Seminar on Precision Optics Manufacturing* vol 11171
- [16] Beck J V and Woodbury K A 1998 Inverse problems and parameter estimation: integration of measurements and analysis *Meas. Sci. Technol.* **9** 839
- [17] Van den Bos A 2007 *Parameter Estimation for Scientists and Engineers* (Wiley)
- [18] O'Hagan A 2008 The Bayesian approach to statistics *Handbook of Probability: Theory and Applications* (SAGE Publications, Inc.) pp 85–100
- [19] Müller E, Nobach H and Tropea C 1998 Model parameter estimation from non-equidistant sampled data sets at low data rates *Meas. Sci. Technol.* **9** 435–41
- [20] Liang H and Wu H 2008 Parameter estimation for differential equation models using a framework of measurement error in regression models *J. Am. Stat. Assoc.* **103** 1570–83
- [21] Rousseeuw P J 1990 *Handbook of Statistical Methods for Engineers and Scientists* (McGraw-Hill)
- [22] Kok G, Wübbeler G and Elster C 2022 Impact of imperfect artefacts and the modus operandi on uncertainty quantification using virtual instruments *Metrology* **2** 311–9
- [23] Kok G, van Dijk M, Wübbeler G and Elster C 2023 Virtual experiments for the assessment of data analysis and uncertainty quantification methods in scatterometry *Metrologia* **60** 044001
- [24] Long J S and Ervin L H 2000 Using heteroscedasticity consistent standard errors in the linear regression model *Am. Stat.* **54** 217–24
- [25] Shemyakin A and Kniazev A 2017 *Introduction to Bayesian Estimation and Copula Models of Dependence* (Wiley)
- [26] Martin A, Parry M, Soundy A W R, Panckhurst B J, Brown P, Molteno T C A and Schumayer D 2020 Improving real-time position estimation using correlated noise models *Sensors* **20** 5913
- [27] Scholz G, Fortmeier I, Marschall M, Stavridis M, Schulz M and Elster C 2022 Experimental design for virtual experiments in tilted-wave interferometry *Metrology* **2** 84–97
- [28] Lindley D V and Smith A F M 1972 Bayes estimates for the linear model *J. R. Stat. Soc. B* **34** 1–41
- [29] BIPM, IEC, IFCC, ILAC, ISO, IUPAC, IUPAP and OIML 2008 *Evaluation of Measurement Data—Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement* (Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, JCGM 100:2008) (available at: www.bipm.org/documents/20126/2071204/JCGM_100_2008_E.pdf/cb0ef43f-baa5-11cf-3f85-4dcd86f77bd6)
- [30] BIPM, IEC, IFCC, ILAC, ISO, IUPAC, IUPAP and OIML 2008 *Evaluation of Measurement Data—Supplement 1 to the “Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement”—Propagation of Distributions Using a Monte Carlo Method* (Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, JCGM 101:2008) (available at: www.bipm.org/documents/20126/2071204/JCGM_101_2008_E.pdf/325dcaad-c15a-407c-1105-8b7f322d651c)
- [31] BIPM, IEC, IFCC, ILAC, ISO, IUPAC, IUPAP and OIML 2011 *Evaluation of Measurement Data—Supplement 2 to the “Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement”—Extension to any Number of Output Quantities* (Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, JCGM 102:2011) (available at: www.bipm.org/documents/20126/2071204/JCGM_102_2011_E.pdf/6a3281aa-1397-d703-d7a1-a8d58c9bf2a5)
- [32] Bich W, Cox M and Michotte C 2016 Towards a new GUM—an update *Metrologia* **53** S149
- [33] Elster C and Toman B 2009 Bayesian uncertainty analysis under prior ignorance of the measurand versus analysis using the supplement 1 to the guide: a comparison *Metrologia* **46** 261
- [34] Elster C 2014 Bayesian uncertainty analysis compared with the application of the GUM and its supplements *Metrologia* **51** S159
- [35] Pruss C, Baer G B, Schindler J and Osten W 2017 Measuring aspheres quickly: tilted wave interferometry *Opt. Eng.* **56** 111713
- [36] Fortmeier I, Stavridis M, Schulz M and Elster C 2022 Development of a metrological reference system for the form measurement of aspheres and freeform surfaces based on a tilted-wave interferometer *Meas. Sci. Technol.* **33** 045013
- [37] O'Sullivan F 1995 A study of least squares and maximum likelihood for image reconstruction in positron emission tomography *Ann. Stat.* **23** 1267–300
- [38] Stuart A M 2010 Inverse problems: a Bayesian perspective *Acta Numer.* **19** 451–559
- [39] Latz J 2023 Bayesian inverse problems are usually well-posed *SIAM Rev.* **65** 831–65
- [40] Robert C P and Casella G 1999 *Monte Carlo Statistical Methods* vol 2 (Springer)